

Recent advances in the applications of the intramolecular Suzuki cross-coupling reaction in cyclization and heterocyclization: An update

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Abstract

The palladium-catalyzed reaction of aryl halide and boronic acid for the formation of C–C bonds so-called Suzuki–Miyaura cross-coupling reaction has many applications in Modern Synthetic Organic Chemistry. In 2013, we emphasized the applications of the intramolecular Suzuki cross-coupling reaction in cyclization and heterocyclization. Due to a plethora relevant papers appeared in the chemical literature, herein, we wish to cover by updating our previous review, the applications of the intramolecular Suzuki cross-coupling reaction in cyclization and heterocyclization leading to various homocyclic and heterocyclic compounds reported during a period of 2013 to 2018.

Keywords: Aza-heterocycles, Carbon-Carbon bond formation, Cyclization, Heterocyclization, Oxa-heterocycles, PalladiumPd-catalyzed reactions, Suzuki cross-coupling reaction